

Methodology for Evaluating Crop Homogeneity Using HHI (Herfindahl-Hirschman Index) Applied to NDVI

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Abstract

This document describes a methodology for assessing crop homogeneity through the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) applied to NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) values. The approach includes (i) collecting NDVI values within an area of interest, (ii) clustering using *k-means* (with user-defined k , default is 5), (iii) flattening to 1D to ignore spatial coordinates, and (iv) calculating the HHI based on the proportion of pixels in each cluster. Results demonstrate how the HHI can indicate higher or lower homogeneity in the distribution of NDVI values across the crop field.

1 Introduction

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is widely used in agricultural monitoring to estimate plant vigor. NDVI interpretation in crop fields can indicate differences in development, water stress, pest occurrences, and other management variables. However, with large datasets, there arises a need for a metric that synthesizes the degree of homogeneity or dispersion of NDVI values.

The Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), originally developed for market concentration analysis, can be adapted to measure the concentration or dispersion of data distributions, such as NDVI. A high HHI indicates that few values (or groups of

values) dominate the distribution, while a low HHI suggests greater diversity. This methodology outlines a step-by-step process for applying the HHI to NDVI, using *k-means* as the clustering technique.

2 Methodology

2.1 NDVI Collection and Polygon Definition

- **Data Source:** Satellite images (e.g., Sentinel-2, Landsat, Planet), drone images with multispectral cameras, or any sensor providing NDVI.
- **Area of Interest (AOI):** Defines the agricultural area (crop field) to analyze homogeneity. This can be a shapefile, GeoJSON, or similar format.
- **Mask for Invalid Data (optional):** Pixels with clouds or anomalous NDVI values should be removed or marked as *NaN* to ensure data quality.

2.2 *Flattening* NDVI to 1D

Once the NDVI data is cropped to the AOI, we obtain a 2D `ndvi_array` (rows and columns). To focus only on the numerical values:

1. Convert the 2D array into a 1D array (*flatten*), and remove *NaN* values (if any):

```
ndvi_flat = ndvi_array.flatten()
ndvi_flat = ndvi_flat[~np.isnan(ndvi_flat)]
```

2. The result is a sequence of NDVI values (N values), disregarding coordinates (x, y) .

2.3 Clustering with *k-means*

Examples of applying *k-means* to cluster NDVI values in crops include the work of Johann et al. (2013) [1], where the algorithm was used to define NDVI ranges and characterize spatial variability within the field. This methodology applies *k-means* to group NDVI values into data-driven ranges:

- The user defines k (number of clusters); by default, $k = 5$.

- The 1D array must be reshaped to $(N, 1)$ for use with `scikit-learn`:

```
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans

X = ndvi_flat.reshape(-1, 1)
kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=5, random_state=42)
labels = kmeans.fit_predict(X)
```

- Each pixel receives a label $0 \dots k - 1$, representing its assigned cluster.

2.4 Calculating the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI)

Although the HHI was initially designed for measuring concentration in business contexts, its use for spatial distribution analysis based on vegetation data is exemplified by Cai et al. (2021) [2]. In this methodology, the HHI is calculated alongside NDVI clusters as:

$$\text{HHI} = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i^2,$$

where α_i is the fraction of pixels in cluster i . If n_i is the number of pixels in cluster i and N is the total number of pixels, $\alpha_i = \frac{n_i}{N}$.

Code example:

```
import numpy as np

counts = np.bincount(labels)
total_pixels = len(labels)
fractions = counts / total_pixels
hhi = np.sum(fractions**2)

print("Fractions per cluster:", fractions)
print("HHI =", hhi)
```

3 Results and Discussion

A high HHI (close to 1) indicates that one or few NDVI ranges dominate the field, suggesting a more uniform crop. If this concentration occurs in high NDVI ranges, the area may be healthy and homogeneous. Conversely, a low HHI (close to 0)

denotes greater dispersion of values, indicating heterogeneity or significant variability in conditions within the area (e.g., localized stress, planting gaps, soil fertility differences).

Through this metric, it is possible to compare the same field on different dates or different areas, observing whether the crop tends to homogenize over the season or shows increasing NDVI dispersion, which may require targeted interventions.

4 Conclusion

This work proposes adapting the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) for assessing NDVI homogeneity in crop fields. The processing workflow includes:

1. Collecting NDVI (from any source) within an area of interest.
2. Flattening NDVI values into 1D for numerical analysis.
3. Clustering with *k-means*, allowing data-driven definition of NDVI ranges.
4. Calculating the HHI based on cluster fractions.

The HHI variation indicates the degree of concentration of NDVI values: closer to 1, the field is more uniform; lower HHI values suggest heterogeneity. Adopting this metric aids in risk mapping, targeted management, and contributes to more efficient precision agriculture.

References

- [1] JOHANN, J. A.; ROCHA, J. V.; LAMPARELLI, R. A. C.; OLIVEIRA, S. R. M. *Data mining techniques for identification of spectrally homogeneous areas using NDVI temporal profiles of soybean crop*. Engenharia Agrícola, v. 33, n. 3, p. 559–569, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-69162013000300008>
- [2] CAI, X.; LI, X.; LIANG Y. *Tempo-spatial changes of ecological vulnerability in the arid area based on ordered weighted average model*. Ecological Indicators, v. 133, 125:108398, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108398>